

ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The decisions of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted within the framework of its powers are mandatory for implementation by state and economic management bodies, state and local government bodies, economic entities, regardless of their forms of ownership and departmental subordination. In the article, the author analyzed the strategic directions of tourism development in Uzbekistan.

Key words: tourism, strategy, economy, currency, income, transport, hotel, management, marketing, free tourist zone.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Turizmni rivojlantirish davlat qo'mitasi-ning o'z vakolatlari doirasida qabul qilgan qarorlari davlat va xo'jalik boshqaruvi organlari, davlat hokimiyati va mahalliy boshqaruv organlari, mulkchilik shakllari va idoraviy bo'ysunishidan qat'i nazar, xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar tomonidan bajarilishi majburiy hisoblanadi. Maqolada muallif O'zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirishning strategik yo'nalishlarini tahlil etgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, strategiya, iqtisodiyot, valyuta, daromad, transport, mehmonxona, menejment, marketing, erkin turistik zona.

Аннотация: Решения Государственного комитета Республики Узбекистан по развитию туризма, принятые в пределах его полномочий, обязательны для исполнения органами государственного и хозяйственного управления, органами государственной власти и управления на местах, субъектами предпринимательства независимо от форм собственности и ведомственной подчиненности. В статье автор проанализировал стратегические направления развития туризма в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: туризм, стратегия, экономика, валюта, доход, транспорт, гостиница, управление, маркетинг, свободная туристическая зона.

Introduction. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been paying special attention to the development of tourism as one of the important sectors of the economy. The country's rich historical heritage, cultural monuments, natural beauty and hospitable people create great potential for tourism.

Economic growth can be ensured by effectively using these opportunities, modernizing tourism infrastructure and increasing the number of foreign and domestic tourists. In this sense, identifying and analyzing strategic directions for tourism development is of not only practical but also scientific importance. This article analyzes the main strategies aimed at developing tourism in Uzbekistan, their effectiveness, as well as existing problems and promising directions.

Main part. The decisions of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted within the framework of its powers are mandatory for implementation by state and economic management bodies, state authorities and local government bodies, economic entities, regardless of their forms of ownership and departmental subordination.

At the same time, the following are the strategic directions for the development of tourism:

→ creating favorable economic and organizational and legal conditions for the rapid development of tourism as a strategic sector of the country's economy, effectively using the tourist resources of the regions, radically improving the management of the tourism industry, and forming a positive image of Uzbekistan in the tourism sector:

→ forming and consistently implementing a comprehensive concept for the development of tourism, giving tourism the status of a strategic sector of the economy, turning this sector into a leading force in the complex and rapid development of all regions and related sectors, increasing the share of tourism in GDP and local budget revenues;

→ further improvement of the legislative and regulatory framework in the field of tourism activities aimed at creating favorable conditions for tourism industry entities, simplification of visa and registration, passport and customs control, optimization of the mechanism of state management of the tourism sector, improvement of the statistical accounting system in the tourism sector;

→ intensive development of tourism in the country, effective use of tourism potential, intensive development of pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, medical and health, rural, business tourism and other types of tourism along with traditional cultural and historical tourism, strengthening the social significance of tourism through the development of children, adolescents and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly, organization of new tourism destinations in the regions, development and implementation of national and regional programs for the integrated development of tourism;

- expanding international cooperation in tourism, primarily with the UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), with influential international and national organizations of foreign countries in the field of tourism, Uzbekistan's participation in universal international conventions and agreements regulating the field of tourism, introducing international and interstate standards and norms into the practice of tourism activities;
- accelerated development of tourism industry facilities in all regions of the republic that meet modern world standards, the needs and requirements of tourists - hotels and accommodation facilities, catering facilities, transport structures, information centers, cultural and sports institutions, accelerated construction and reconstruction of engineering and communication infrastructure, and widespread attraction of foreign investors for these purposes;
- taking into account the trends in the development of international tourism and the use of modern marketing tools, developing a strategy for the development of competitive tourism products and services, promoting them in the domestic and international tourism markets, organizing and developing a favorable tourism information environment, carrying out extensive advertising and information activities, opening tourism information centers in the regions of the country and tourism representative offices abroad;
- radically improving the system of high-quality training of qualified personnel for the tourism industry, especially in the field of management and marketing, training guides, and improving the systems of regular retraining and advanced training of employees of tourism entities were set as the main tasks

Figure 1. Strategic directions for tourism development in Uzbekistan¹

At the same time, new directions, which are the most relevant and unprecedented in Uzbek tourism, have also begun to be introduced. Based on the Decree of our President dated December 5, 2017 No. PF-5273 "On the establishment of the "Chorvak" free tourist zone", in order to further develop the tourist potential of our republic and increase the efficiency of its use, create favorable conditions for attracting foreign and domestic tourists to the region, ensure the rapid development of modern infrastructure, expand and improve the quality of the provided tourist, hotel and transport services, the "Chorvak" free tourist zone was established within the borders of the Chimyon-Chorvak resort and recreation zone of the Tashkent region. It was determined to build modern hotel complexes, other cultural, recreational, trade, entertainment and tourist facilities on the territory of the FTZ, as well as to establish modern engineering infrastructure facilities.²

Based on this:

↳ attracting investments from foreign and local investors to implement projects to create modern tourism infrastructure facilities (hotel complexes, cultural and recreational, trade and entertainment and other facilities of tourist importance) in the ETZ, special functional and seasonal recreational zones with the necessary conditions for servicing tourists; organizing unique tourist routes taking into account the ecological potential of the region; ensuring the affordability of transport, introducing new types of transport in the region (electric train, bus), including those powered by alternative energy sources,

expanding passenger transport routes, organizing its uninterrupted movement, developing the appropriate transport infrastructure;

↳ creating additional conditions for tourist safety, including equipping tourist infrastructure facilities with video surveillance systems, organizing warning systems, introducing a single database of tourists visiting the region, and an emergency assistance system;

↳ to provide separate customs and tax regimes for business entities implementing and operating projects and investors (including foreign investors) in the territory of the free tourist zone;

↳ to implement projects to create a unique ecological system based on the pilot introduction of new modern energy-saving systems and technologies using alternative and renewable energy sources.

Most importantly, the provisions of the legislation on free economic zones were applied to business entities registered as participants in the FTZ, including all the privileges and preferences provided for free economic zones and their participants.

At the same time, one of the most important aspects of this stage was the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Tourism” No. URQ-549 on July 18, 2019, which was updated and revised to regulate tourist activities.

As can be seen from the above, today the process of forming a national tourism model in Uzbekistan is being carried out with great intensity. In the conditions of the formation of a market economy in the republic, tourism remains an important factor in stabilizing the national economy based on its redistribution of national income. In a market economy, tourists are mainly served by private and commercial companies.

In addition, tourism will develop stably if the state creates a favorable economic and legal atmosphere. On the other hand, if the state does not deal with the problems of professional training, protection of the natural and cultural environment, information and advertising work, and simplification of formalities, tourism will not reach the required level of development under the rule of market forces alone. In this regard, the state should attach importance to the development of appropriate methodological and practical approaches and the organization of the tourist services market.

Conclusions and recommendations. In conclusion, despite the great potential of Uzbekistan in the field of tourism, a strategic approach is required for its further development. As a result of the reforms implemented in recent years, the tourism infrastructure, legislative framework and marketing activities

have significantly improved. However, the existing opportunities have not been fully utilized, the infrastructure in some regions is underdeveloped, and the quality of service still lags behind international standards.

In this regard, the following recommendations can be put forward:

1. Increase attention to the development of regional tourism - it is necessary to activate the local tourism network by identifying and promoting the unique tourist resources of each region.

2. Improve personnel training and service quality - it is important to improve the system of training qualified specialists for the tourism sector, organize practical training for existing employees.

3. Introduction of digital technologies - it is necessary to create convenience for tourists through online booking systems, digital guides, mobile applications and other innovative tools.

4. Strengthening international promotion - through effective advertising of Uzbekistan's historical and cultural heritage in foreign markets, it is possible to increase the flow of tourists.

5. Developing public-private partnerships - it is necessary to introduce incentive mechanisms to expand the participation of the private sector in the construction and development of tourism facilities.

These measures will ensure the sustainable development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan and make it one of the leading sectors of the economy.

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